

Africans in Stuart England: mapping their individual and collective narratives.

There is a significant gap in Black British historiography that leaves the presence of Africans in Stuart England remarkably unexplored. While quantifying their presence would fill this gap, technology enables a reimagination of England's early modern streets and parishes focusing on individual historical figures. My research combines digital techniques with traditional historiographical practices to diversify and up-end the way in which we think about English history.

On November 5th, 1605, a group of Catholics planned to blow up the English parliament; a date we all remember with the popular rhyme, 'Remember, Remember, the 5th of November'. On the same day, Constantyn, described as 'a negare out of ye pylgrme of portmouthe' was buried in the London parish of St Olave, Tooley Street. We may never know why Constantyn travelled to London or why she was subsequently buried there but her presence is important. Constantyn was one of hundreds of African individuals who lived and died in early modern England.

Although individual narratives are at the forefront of my research, I aim to avoid African exceptionalism: a flawed historical practice which separates diasporic African individuals from their social, economic, and cultural environments. Fully integrating mentions of Africans in early modern records will contextualise their lived experiences whilst adding weight to the argument that they were not all enslaved as is often assumed. My research emphasises how inclusion paradoxically went hand in hand with the global development of racist ideologies.

Mapping Black Africans in Tudor and Stuart England allows for a unique assessment of the statuses they assumed and the spaces they occupied in early modern English society. I explore how we can make historical data more accessible, while both posing and answering new questions about Black British History. Where in England did Africans live? Were these locations linked to the prevalent port towns in particular periods? Was there geographical mobility for Africans once they arrived in England? My research examines the social, economic, and racial contexts and spaces in which these individuals lived to demonstrate the existence of a multi-ethnic early modern England.

This paper explores the source types through which a Black Stuart presence can be seen. It showcases a substantial database of records including ranging from parish records, wills, tax returns, diary entries and newspaper articles. Through these sources, individual narratives are uncovered, enabling a reimagining of this particular epoch of British history. With handfuls of individuals able to make livings for themselves and express agency throughout Stuart England, assertions that they were enslaved need to be readdressed. Analysing the seventeenth century, a period of growth and escalation for the trans-Atlantic slave trade, allows for a comparative study of the status of Africans in English communities and Africans in English colonies overseas. Were Africans labelled as chattel in England, at what point, and why? While addressing these questions through traditional historiographical methods, the maps showcased in this paper stand as irrefutable and accessible visual proofs that Africans lived and worked in Tudor & Stuart England.